

Cooperative Integer Programming Games: Core Stability and Optimal Coalition Structures

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Abstract. In cooperative game theory, a characteristic-function game is defined by a set of agents N and a characteristic function V that assigns to each coalition $c \subseteq N$ a real value $V(c)$, i.e., $V : 2^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. We focus on resource-sharing settings in which coalitions accomplish indivisible (integer) tasks: agents pool their constraints to satisfy integer feasibility jointly and budget constraints at the coalition level, after which the resulting value can be split continuously among members. We introduce *cooperative integer programming games* (CIPGs), in which each coalition has its own integer programming model and the characteristic function V maps every coalition c to the optimal value of the corresponding pooled or individual integer program. Our primary goal is to identify an optimal coalition structure (OCS) and an OCS satisfying stability (OCSS). We derive a *stability inequality* that guarantees stability within each coalition—meaning each coalition is in the Core with respect to itself. Building on this inequality, we develop a cutting-plane algorithm to compute OCSS, in which the initial agent set is partitioned into coalitions that satisfy the stability condition. Computational experiments on cooperative knapsack games demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method in finding OCSS solutions.

Key words: Integer programming games, Cooperative game theory, Optimal coalition structure, Stability

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation and research question

In many multi-agent systems, each player faces an individual resource-allocation problem that is naturally modeled as an integer program—for example, a knapsack or capacity-constrained selection problem. Acting alone, a player may be unable to activate certain indivisible items or projects because their budget is insufficient. By forming a coalition and pooling their budgets, players can satisfy these integer requirements jointly and then share the resulting value continuously.

Such situations arise naturally in practice. Consider, for example, a group of municipalities deciding which infrastructure projects (bridge upgrades, water-treatment plants) to fund: each project requires an indivisible investment, and individual budgets may be insufficient, but a coalition of municipalities can pool funds to activate projects that benefit all members. Similar settings appear in joint procurement (firms pooling orders to meet minimum batch sizes), collaborative R&D (research groups sharing equipment budgets to fund discrete experiments), and shared logistics (carriers pooling capacity to serve indivisible shipment requests).

This motivates our *cooperative integer programming games* (CIPGs). The player set is N , and for each coalition $c \subseteq N$ the characteristic function $V(c)$ is defined as the optimal value of a coalition-level integer program obtained from the members' individual models by (i) pooling budget-type constraints and (ii) preserving player-specific structural constraints. Thus, CIPGs retain

the characteristic-function framework, but the values $V(c)$ are generated by solving integer programs rather than being given in closed form as is common in classical cooperative games. Because each coalition value is defined through an optimization problem, structural properties of V such as superadditivity, convexity, and non-emptiness of the Core are no longer guaranteed by the framework; they depend on each problem's underlying characteristics, including its pooling rules and coalition-level bound restrictions.

Throughout the paper we investigate the following research questions: (i) What structural properties of the characteristic function V (e.g., monotonicity, superadditivity, convexity) can be established in CIPGs? (ii) How can we model and compute an *optimal coalition structure* (OCS) for a given set N ? (iii) How can we characterize and compute coalition structures with stability (CSS), and how can we *optimize* over CSSs to obtain an *optimal coalition structure with stability* (OCSS)?

For the stability question, we first recall the central solution concept. Given a coalition $c \subseteq N$ with characteristic function V , the *Core* of c is the set of payoff vectors $\{v \in \mathbb{R}^{|c|} : \sum_{i \in c} v_i = V(c) \text{ and } \sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s) \text{ for all } s \subseteq c\}$; i.e., the payoffs are *efficient* (they exhaust the coalition value) and *stable* (no subcoalition can profitably deviate). A *coalition structure* (CS) over c is a partition $CS(c) = \{c_1, \dots, c_k\}$ with $\bigsqcup_{\ell=1}^k c_\ell = c$ and $c_\ell \cap c_m = \emptyset$ for all $\ell \neq m$. We adopt *coalition-structure stability* (Kóczy 2018): a coalition structure $CS(N) = \{c_1, \dots, c_k\}$ together with a payoff vector v is a CSS if, for each coalition c_ℓ , the restriction of v to c_ℓ lies in the Core of the game restricted to c_ℓ . Because the Core condition is enforced *within* each coalition, CSS guards against fission (splitting)—no subcoalition has an incentive to break away—but does not guard against fusion (merging), i.e., separate coalitions may still benefit from merging (Yang 2025). We refer to any CSS that maximizes total payoff $\sum_{i \in N} v_i$ as an OCSS. Our algorithms are designed to directly optimize over CSS-feasible solutions.

1.2. Literature Review

The coalition-structure generation (CSG) problem seeks a partition of N that maximizes social welfare when the values $V(c)$ are assumed given, either explicitly or via a simple formula (Sandholm et al. 1999, Rahwan et al. 2009, 2015). A parallel line develops stability notions for games with coalition structures: Aumann and Drèze (1974) extend classical solution concepts to arbitrary partitions, Kóczy (2018) defines the coalition structure core for partition function form games, and Apt and Radzik (2006), Apt and Witzel (2009) study stable partitions via defection functions. Building on these foundations, CIPGs treat each $V(c)$ as the optimal value of a coalition-level integer program, so value generation itself is NP-hard and must be integrated with coalition-structure and stability computations.

Classical combinatorial optimization games define $V(c)$ via a fixed combinatorial problem on a graph or network (Borm et al. 2001, Chalkiadakis et al. 2011), and many core-related questions can be handled using specialized combinatorial structure (Deng et al. 1999). Our CIPG framework generalizes beyond these graph-based models: each player solves their own resource-constrained integer program, and each coalition c solves a new pooled integer program to obtain $V(c)$.

Cooperative games with optimization-based characteristic functions appear in several domains, including water-resources management (Wang et al. 2003), electricity transmission cost allocation (Stamtsis and Erlich 2004), waste-management planning (Eryganov et al. 2020), and shared energy-storage investments (Wang et al. 2024). These models illustrate the practical relevance of cooperative optimization, but they typically rely on linear or continuous formulations and do not treat each agent's decision problem as an integer program. CIPGs can be viewed as a unifying abstraction for such applications when indivisibilities and player-specific integer decisions are essential, and when coalition-level objectives (including regulatory penalties or incentives) must be embedded directly into the optimization.

Axiomatic work on cooperative knapsack allocation, e.g., Arribillaga and Bergantiños (2022), typically considers a *single* knapsack for the grand coalition and studies allocation rules and core properties in that setting; related cost-sharing models also assume a fixed grand coalition (Dror and Trabelsi 1990, Darmann and Klamlr 2014). Our Cooperative Knapsack Game (CKG) differs in three ways: (i) each player starts with their own integer knapsack; (ii) each coalition c solves a coalition-specific 0–1 knapsack IP obtained by pooling members’ capacities; and (iii) we optimize over coalition structures under Core-type stability constraints, rather than proposing allocation axioms for a given grand coalition.

Non-cooperative integer programming games (NCIPGs) model strategic interactions in which each player solves an individual (mixed-)integer program and payoffs are coupled through bilinear or shared-constraint structures (Carvalho et al. 2023). Equilibria are *pure Nash equilibria* (PNE), typically computed via cutting-plane–based zero-regret methods (Dragotto and Scatamacchia 2023) and best-response algorithms (Lee et al. 2024). These models do not form coalitions and do not consider Core or partition stability. By contrast, CIPGs aggregate players’ integer programs within coalitions and define $V(c)$ via coalition-level optimization, then seek Core-type allocations and partition-stable outcomes (CSS/OCSS). In this sense, CIPGs provide a cooperative counterpart to NCIPGs: Nash equilibrium versus Core-based stability, both grounded in integer-programming formulations.

1.3. Contributions

- We formalize *cooperative integer programming games* (CIPGs), in which each player has an individual resource-allocation integer program and each coalition’s value $V(c)$ is defined by a pooled coalition-level integer program. We explore structural conditions that encompass a range of coalition setups—including how budgets are pooled, how coalition-level bounds are set, and how item access is shared—and characterize when the grand coalition is necessarily optimal versus when nontrivial coalition structures can arise.
- We propose a mixed-integer *optimal coalition structure* (OCS) formulation that embeds coalition-level integer programs for all potential coalitions via assignment and resource-pooling constraints. We derive a family of *stability inequalities* that enforce Core constraints within each formed coalition and design a separation oracle that, given a current coalition structure and payoffs, solves a coalition-level optimization problem to detect violated inequalities. Implemented as lazy constraints, this yields a cutting-plane algorithm that directly optimizes over CSS-feasible solutions and returns an OCSS.
- We instantiate the framework as a Cooperative Knapsack Game (CKG), where players have individual 0–1 knapsacks and coalitions pool capacities under either natural coalition bounds or restricted bounds on common items. Computational experiments demonstrate that our algorithm can compute OCSS solutions for instances with multiple players and nontrivial coalition structures.

2. Cooperative Integer Programming Games

2.1. Player- and coalition-level integer programs

We first present a canonical knapsack-type CIPG in which each player has a single budget constraint. The framework, however, readily extends to more general integer programs with additional player-specific constraints. For each player $i \in N$ and resource $j \in R$, let $x_j^i \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ denote the amount of resource j chosen by player i , with profit coefficient p_j^i and common weight $a_j > 0$. Each player

has an individual budget b^i and possibly additional private constraints $B^i x^i \leq d^i$. The individual problem of player i is

$$V(i) = \max \left\{ \sum_{j \in R} p_j^i x_j^i : \sum_{j \in R} a_j x_j^i \leq b^i, x_j^i \in \mathbb{Z}_+ \forall j \in R, B^i x^i \leq d^i \right\}. \quad (1)$$

When a coalition $c \subseteq N$ forms, its members pool their budgets $\{b^i\}_{i \in c}$ but retain their individual constraints $B^i x^i \leq d^i$. Not every player in c necessarily has access to every item j . For each coalition $c \subseteq N$ and item $j \in R$, let $I_j^c \subseteq c$ denote the set of players in c for whom item j is available. We then define the coalition-specific resource set $R^c := \{j \in R : I_j^c \neq \emptyset\}$. We partition R^c into two sets: R_{com}^c is the set of indices $j \in R^c$ corresponding to resources that are *common* within coalition c , and $R_{\text{ind}}^c := R^c \setminus R_{\text{com}}^c$ is the set of indices treated as individual-specific. The key difference lies in integrality: for common items $j \in R_{\text{com}}^c$, integrality is enforced on the coalition-level aggregate $y_j^c = \sum_{i \in I_j^c} x_j^i$, while the player-level variables x_j^i may be continuous; for individual items $j \in R_{\text{ind}}^c$, each x_j^i is itself integer.

For common items, we introduce coalition-level auxiliary variables $y_j^c = \sum_{i \in I_j^c} x_j^i$, $j \in R_{\text{com}}^c$, which aggregate total usage of item j in coalition c . Integrality is enforced on the coalition variables y_j^c , while the player-level variables x_j^i for $j \in R_{\text{com}}^c$ may be relaxed to be continuous. This formulation reflects the two-stage nature of coalition decisions: first, the coalition makes an integer commitment on how many units of each common item to activate (captured by $y_j^c \in \mathbb{Z}_+$); then, the resulting value is allocated continuously among the contributing members (captured by continuous $x_j^i \geq 0$ with $\sum_{i \in I_j^c} x_j^i = y_j^c$). The individual-specific items in R_{ind}^c retain integrality since they are decided by a single player.

The coalition value $V(c)$ is then given by the coalition-level integer program

$$V(c) = \max \sum_{j \in R_{\text{com}}^c} \sum_{i \in I_j^c} p_j^i x_j^i + \sum_{j \in R_{\text{ind}}^c} \sum_{i \in I_j^c} p_j^i x_j^i \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{j \in R_{\text{com}}^c} a_j y_j^c + \sum_{j \in R_{\text{ind}}^c} \sum_{i \in I_j^c} a_j x_j^i \leq \sum_{i \in c} b^i, \quad (2b)$$

$$y_j^c = \sum_{i \in I_j^c} x_j^i, \quad \forall j \in R_{\text{com}}^c, \quad (2c)$$

$$B^i x^i \leq d^i, \quad \forall i \in c, \quad (2d)$$

$$x_j^i \geq 0, \quad \forall i \in c, j \in R_{\text{com}}^c, \quad (2e)$$

$$y_j^c \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \quad \forall j \in R_{\text{com}}^c, \quad x_j^i \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \quad \forall i \in c, j \in R_{\text{ind}}^c. \quad (2f)$$

In Sections 2.2 and 2.3, we analyze the structural properties of the resulting characteristic function V and formulate the optimal coalition structure (OCS) problem. The proofs for the canonical knapsack case extend directly to (1)–(2) because the additional constraints $B^i x^i \leq d^i$ remain player-specific and are not pooled at the coalition level.

REMARK 1 (GENERALITY BEYOND KNAPSACK-TYPE CONSTRAINTS). Our framework does not rely on the specific single-knapsack constraint plus side constraints $B^i x^i \leq d^i$. The OCS formulation and stability inequality in Sections 2.3–2.4 only require that, for each coalition $c \subseteq N$, $V(c)$ is defined as the optimal value of a coalition-level integer program. In particular, each player's problem can be written in the general form $\max\{(p^i)^\top x^i : A^i x^i \leq b^i, x^i \in \mathbb{Z}_+^{n_i}\}$, where some rows of $A^i x^i \leq b^i$ correspond to consumable resources that are pooled, and the rest encode non-pooled

structural constraints. The structural results in Section 2.2 (e.g., Proposition 1) additionally assume nonnegative profits $p_j^i \geq 0$; however, the embedding argument used in the proof of Proposition 1 places no sign restriction on the constraint coefficients A^i . The OCS formulation and stability results in Sections 2.3–2.4 hold for any characteristic function generated by coalition-level integer programs. We focus on the knapsack-type CIPG for clarity and for our computational study.

2.2. Structural properties of the characteristic function V

Before developing optimization and stability machinery, we examine how the structural properties of V vary with the underlying coalition policies. In practice, coalition bounds and coalition-level objectives can differ depending on pooling arrangements, resource-sharing rules, and institutional constraints. The analysis below shows that under natural coalition bounds, V is superadditive (and the OCS is trivially the grand coalition), while restricted bounds or coalition-level penalties can break superadditivity, making the OCS instance-dependent. This dichotomy motivates the algorithmic framework in the remainder of the paper.

A key question in cooperative integer programming games is which structural properties the characteristic function $V : 2^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies. We briefly recall four standard notions.

DEFINITION 1 (MONOTONICITY, SUBADDITIVITY, SUPERADDITIVITY, CONVEXITY). Let (N, V) be a cooperative game with $V : 2^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $V(\emptyset) = 0$.

- *Monotonicity*: $S \subseteq T \Rightarrow V(S) \leq V(T)$.
- *Subadditivity*: $V(S \cup T) \leq V(S) + V(T)$ for all disjoint S, T .
- *Superadditivity*: $V(S \cup T) \geq V(S) + V(T)$ for all disjoint S, T .
- *Convexity (supermodularity)*: $V(S) + V(T) \leq V(S \cup T) + V(S \cap T)$ for all S, T .

Convexity is the strongest of these properties: convex games are superadditive and, under mild assumptions such as nonnegative singleton values, also monotone. Superadditivity implies that merging coalitions is beneficial at the level of total value: for any partition $CS = \{c_1, \dots, c_k\}$ of N , repeated application of superadditivity shows that the grand coalition $\{N\}$ achieves value at least as large as $\sum_{\ell=1}^k V(c_\ell)$. Thus, in a superadditive game, the OCS is trivially the grand coalition. Similarly, if V is subadditive, splitting coalitions is never harmful: for any coalition c and any partition of c into smaller coalitions, subadditivity implies $V(c) \leq \sum_{i \in c} V(\{i\})$, so the partition into singleton coalitions $\{\{i\} : i \in N\}$ maximizes $\sum_c V(c)$. In a purely subadditive game (with no other structure), the OCS is therefore the collection of self-coalitions.

In CIPGs, these properties are *not* fixed: they depend on the coalition setups governing the coalition-level integer program (2), including bounds on coalition-level variables and additional terms in the objective. Rather than attempting an exhaustive characterization, we highlight representative scenarios that can arise.

(i) Natural coalition bounds. We first add upper bounds $x_j^i \leq u_j^i$ to the player- and coalition-level problems (1)–(2). Under *natural* coalition bounds, a coalition can use the full sum of its members’ individual “capacity” on each common item: $0 \leq y_j^c \leq \sum_{i \in I_j^c} u_j^i$, $y_j^c \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, $\forall c \subseteq N$, $\forall j \in R_{\text{com}}^c$. With nonnegative profits p_j^i and $V(\emptyset) = 0$, monotonicity is immediate: if $S \subseteq T$, we can embed any feasible solution of the coalition problem for S into that of T by setting all variables of players in $T \setminus S$ to zero, so $V(S) \leq V(T)$. Moreover, in this “fully pooled” regime, the characteristic function V is superadditive. The following proposition is elementary but plays a key role: it shows that under natural coalition bounds the OCS is *trivially* the grand coalition, thereby motivating the restricted-bound setting in which nontrivial coalition structures arise.

PROPOSITION 1 (Superadditivity under natural coalition bounds). Assume that for every coalition $c \subseteq N$ and item j , the variables satisfy $0 \leq x_j^i \leq u_j^i$ and $0 \leq y_j^c \leq \sum_{i \in c} u_j^i$, with profits

$p_j^i \geq 0$. Then the characteristic function V is superadditive, i.e., $V(c \cup d) \geq V(c) + V(d)$ for all disjoint $c, d \subseteq N$.

Proof Let $c, d \subseteq N$ be disjoint. Take optimal solutions (x^c, y^c) for $V(c)$ and (x^d, y^d) for $V(d)$. Define a candidate solution for $c \cup d$ by setting $\hat{x}_j^i = x_j^c$ if $i \in c$, $\hat{x}_j^i = x_j^d$ if $i \in d$, and $\hat{x}_j^i = 0$ otherwise, and $\hat{y}_j^{c \cup d} = y_j^c + y_j^d$. Because c and d are disjoint and $0 \leq x_j^i \leq u_j^i$, we have $0 \leq \hat{x}_j^i \leq u_j^i$ and $0 \leq \hat{y}_j^{c \cup d} \leq \sum_{i \in c} u_j^i + \sum_{i \in d} u_j^i = \sum_{i \in c \cup d} u_j^i$. The capacity constraint for $c \cup d$ is satisfied by summing the capacities of c and d , and all player-specific constraints $B^i x^i \leq d^i$ remain valid since each x^i is unchanged. The objective value of (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) is $V(c) + V(d)$, so by optimality $V(c \cup d) \geq V(c) + V(d)$. Hence V is superadditive. \square

Convexity is not imposed in our model: capacity saturation and overlapping profitable items can make marginal gains decrease when coalitions become large, so convexity generally does not follow from (2).

(ii) Restricted coalition bounds. We next consider *restricted* coalition bounds, where a coalition cannot fully exploit the sum of individual upper bounds. For some $c \subseteq N$ and $j \in R_{\text{com}}^c$, we may impose $0 \leq y_j^c \leq \bar{u}_j^c < \sum_{i \in I_j^c} u_j^i$, or, in the extreme, a binary activation $y_j^c \in \{0, 1\}$ for a shared resource. This setting aligns with applications where certain projects or facilities are globally limited (e.g., a transmission line or reservoir expansion that can only be built once per coalition), even if individual players could afford them separately.

Monotonicity still holds under nonnegative profits: enlarging a coalition never shrinks the feasible region, as we can always keep the extra players at zero decisions. However, superadditivity can fail. A minimal example is the binary common item with two players: each alone can set $x_1^i = 1$ and obtain value 1, but the coalition $\{1, 2\}$ faces a single shared unit $y_1^{\{1,2\}} \in \{0, 1\}$, so the joint value is only $1 < 1 + 1$. In such restricted-bound regimes, the OCS is no longer guaranteed to be the grand coalition; instead, it becomes instance-dependent and nontrivial partitions can outperform $\{N\}$.

(iii) Additional terms in the coalition-level objective. Finally, the coalition-level objective in (2a) can include explicit coalition-level incentives or penalties: $V(c) = V_0(c) + T(c)$, where $V_0(c)$ is the “pure pooling” value from (2) and $T(c)$ captures regulatory, contractual, or administrative effects.

Positive incentives. A regulator may reward coordination through bonuses that depend on coalition size or composition. A simple example is a modular term $T(c) = \gamma|c|$ with $\gamma \geq 0$; since this is additive in players, if V_0 is monotone, superadditive, or convex, then $V(c) = V_0(c) + \gamma|c|$ preserves these properties. More strongly, one can use supermodular bonuses to *promote convexity*, such as $T(c) = \gamma|c|^2$ or $T(c) = \gamma \binom{|c|}{2}$ with $\gamma > 0$, where the marginal bonus of adding a player increases with coalition size, or pairwise synergy terms $T(c) = \sum_{\{i,j\} \subseteq c} \beta_{ij}$ with $\beta_{ij} \geq 0$. In these cases, T itself defines a convex (supermodular) game, and adding T to a convex base game V_0 preserves convexity.

Negative penalties. Conversely, to discourage collusion or excessive market power, a regulator may impose coalition-level penalties, for instance $T(c) = -\lambda(|c| - 1)$ with $\lambda > 0$. For sufficiently large λ , the combined function $V(c) = V_0(c) - \lambda(|c| - 1)$ can become subadditive, so merging coalitions strictly reduces total value and smaller coalitions (possibly singletons) become optimal. Monotonicity may still hold for moderate penalties, but can fail if the penalty dominates players’ marginal contributions.

In summary, CIPGs accommodate a wide range of structural behaviors for V . Under natural coalition bounds and no (or modest, modular) incentives, V is typically monotone and superadditive, making the grand coalition the optimal coalition structure. Under restricted bounds or strong coalition-level penalties, superadditivity can break, convexity may be lost, and the OCS becomes instance-dependent—precisely the regime where our coalition-structure and stability analysis is most informative.

2.3. Optimal coalition structure (OCS) formulation

We now formulate a mixed-integer program that (i) selects a coalition structure (a partition of N), and (ii) solves the coalition-level integer programs for each formed group. We reuse the item set R and availability sets I_j from Section 2.1. Since the partition into common and individual items depends on which coalition forms, we do *not* fix global sets R_{com} and R_{ind} ; instead, the classification is determined endogenously by auxiliary indicator variables (see the discussion after the formulation). Coalitions are represented by group indices $g \in G$: players with $z_{ig} = 1$ form coalition $c(g)$, and the constraints below restrict budgets and item usage to those members.

Table 1 summarizes the notation used in the formulation.

Sets and Indices	
N	set of players; index $i \in N$
$G := N$	set of potential group indices (at most $ N $ groups form)
R	item set
$I_j \subseteq N$	players for which item j is available
Parameters	
p_j^i	profit of item j for player i
a_j	weight (size/cost) of item j (common across players)
b^i	budget/capacity of player i
u_j^i	upper bound on usage of item j by player i
B^i, d^i	matrices/vectors defining additional constraints $B^i x^i \leq d^i$
Decision Variables	
$z_{ig} \in \{0, 1\}$	1 if player i is assigned to group g , 0 otherwise
$x_j^{i,g}$	usage of item j by player i in group g
$y_j^g \in \mathbb{Z}_+$	aggregate usage of item j in group g
$w_j^g \in \{0, 1\}$	1 if item j is common in group g (used by ≥ 2 assigned players)
v_i	payoff allocated to player i
φ_{ig}	linearization auxiliary: $\varphi_{ig} = v_i \cdot z_{ig}$

Table 1 Notation for the OCS formulation.

The OCS problem is:

$$\max \sum_{i \in N} v_i \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{g \in G} z_{ig} = 1, \quad \forall i \in N, \quad (3b)$$

$$\sum_{j \in R} \sum_{i \in I_j} p_j^i x_j^{i,g} = \sum_{i \in N} v_i z_{ig}, \quad \forall g \in G, \quad (3c)$$

$$\sum_{j \in R} a_j y_j^g \leq \sum_{i \in N} b^i z_{ig}, \quad \forall g \in G, \quad (3d)$$

$$y_j^g = \sum_{i \in I_j} x_j^{i,g}, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall j \in R, \quad (3e)$$

$$0 \leq x_j^{i,g} \leq u_j^i z_{ig}, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall j \in R, \forall i \in I_j, \quad (3f)$$

$$B^i x^{i,g} \leq d^i z_{ig}, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall i \in N, \quad (3g)$$

$$y_j^g \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall j \in R, \quad (3h)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I_j} z_{ig} \geq 2 w_j^g, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall j \in R, \quad (3i)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I_j} z_{ig} - 1 \leq (|I_j| - 1) w_j^g, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall j \in R, \quad (3j)$$

$$w_j^g \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall j \in R, \quad (3k)$$

$$z_{ig} = 0, \quad \forall g \in G, \forall i \in N \text{ with } i < g, \quad (3l)$$

$$\sum_{i \in N} z_{ig} \leq |N| z_{gg}, \quad \forall g \in G, \quad (3m)$$

$$z_{ig} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in N, \forall g \in G. \quad (3n)$$

The objective (3a) maximizes the total payoff $\sum_{i \in N} v_i$. Constraint (3b) enforces that each player belongs to exactly one group, so the nonempty groups $\{g \in G : \sum_{i \in N} z_{ig} > 0\}$ induce a coalition structure (a partition of N). The efficiency constraint (3c) equates the total profit of group g (left-hand side) to the total payoff allocated to its members (right-hand side); both sides represent the endogenous coalition value $V(c(g))$ of the realized coalition $c(g) = \{i \in N : z_{ig} = 1\}$. Constraints (3d)–(3h) embed, for each group g , a coalition-level integer program consistent with (1)–(2): the budgets of members assigned to g are pooled on the right-hand side of (3d), items are aggregated through integer coalition variables y_j^g , and player-specific constraints $B^i x^{i,g} \leq d^i$ are preserved via (3g).

In Section 2.1, the sets R_{com}^c and R_{ind}^c are coalition-dependent: item j is common in coalition c if and only if $|I_j \cap c| \geq 2$. Since the coalition structure is itself a decision in the OCS model, this classification must be determined endogenously. We achieve this through the binary indicator variables w_j^g . Constraints (3i)–(3j) enforce that $w_j^g = 1$ if and only if two or more players in I_j are assigned to group g , i.e., $\sum_{i \in I_j} z_{ig} \geq 2$. When $w_j^g = 0$, item j has at most one user in group g and is therefore individual-specific; when $w_j^g = 1$, item j is common in group g . The restricted coalition bounds discussed in Section 2.2 can then be applied selectively: for instance, α -restricted pooling imposes $y_j^g \leq \alpha \sum_{i \in I_j} u_j^i z_{ig} + M_j(1 - w_j^g)$, where $M_j = \sum_{i \in I_j} u_j^i$, so the restriction is active only when

$w_j^g = 1$ (common items) and becomes vacuous for individual items. This endogenous mechanism ensures that the OCS model faithfully captures the coalition-dependent item classification from Section 2.1 without requiring separate global sets R_{com} and R_{ind} .

Constraints (3l)–(3m) implement a *group-leader* symmetry-breaking scheme. Constraint (3l) restricts group g to contain only players with indices $i \geq g$, and (3m) forces player g to belong to group g whenever that group is nonempty ($\sum_i z_{ig} > 0 \Rightarrow z_{gg} = 1$). Thus, each nonempty group has a unique leader—its smallest indexed member—and any coalition structure is represented in a canonical way, reducing symmetric labelings without excluding any feasible partition.

Hence, any optimal solution to (3) yields an optimal coalition structure (OCS) in which every player i belongs to exactly one coalition (including the possibility of a singleton coalition). Moreover, the different structural scenarios for the characteristic function V discussed in Section 2.2 can be incorporated directly into (3): restricted or natural coalition bounds correspond to additional bounds on y_j^g (e.g., $0 \leq y_j^g \leq \bar{u}_j^g$), while regulatory incentives or penalties enter as additional terms on the left-hand side of (3c) (e.g., adding a coalition-level term $T(g)$ to the profit sum).

Note that constraint (3c) involves the product $v_i \cdot z_{ig}$ and is therefore bilinear. We linearize it via standard big- M techniques: for each pair (i, g) , introduce an auxiliary variable $\phi_{ig} = v_i \cdot z_{ig}$ together with the constraints $\phi_{ig} \leq v_i$, $\phi_{ig} \leq M z_{ig}$, $\phi_{ig} \geq v_i - M(1 - z_{ig})$, and $\phi_{ig} \geq 0$, where M is a valid upper bound on the payoff v_i . Since each player’s payoff cannot exceed the value of any coalition it belongs to, a computation-free bound is $M = \sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \in R: i \in I_j} p_j^i u_j^i$, which is derived directly from the input parameters. The right-hand side of constraint (3c) is then replaced by $\sum_{i \in N} \phi_{ig}$. This linearization is standard and is used in our implementation.

2.4. Stability inequality for CSS

The OCS formulation (3) maximizes total coalition value over all partitions of N , but it does *not* enforce stability: a formed coalition may admit a blocking subcoalition that can improve upon the allocated payoffs. We now introduce a family of *stability inequalities* that restrict the OCS model to *coalition structures with stability* (CSS), where every formed coalition is in the Core with respect to itself.

In the OCS formulation (3), each group index $g \in G$ corresponds to a potential coalition $c(g) := \{i \in N : z_{ig} = 1\}$. For each formed coalition $c(g)$, Core stability requires $\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s)$ for all subcoalitions $s \subseteq c(g)$. We want to encode these Core inequalities only when the players in s are indeed together in some coalition $c(g)$. To do this without introducing explicit coalition-indicator variables, we gate the inequalities using the assignment variables z_{ig} .

For each subset $s \subseteq N$, let $M_s \geq V(s)$ be a valid upper bound. For each group $g \in G$ and each subset $s \subseteq c(g)$, we impose the *stability inequality*

$$\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s) - M_s(|s| - \sum_{i \in s} z_{ig}). \quad (4)$$

Note that when $s \subseteq c(g)$, we have $z_{ig} = 1$ for all $i \in s$, so $|s| - \sum_{i \in s} z_{ig} = 0$ and (4) reduces to the Core inequality $\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s)$. When some player in s is not in group g , the gate term is positive, and the right-hand side is relaxed to at most zero; in that case (4) is trivially satisfied and has no effect. Thus (4) is an algebraic encoding of the Core constraints for all subcoalitions $s \subseteq c(g)$. We note that the big- M formulation (4) can yield a weak LP relaxation when M_s is large relative to $V(s)$. Since the separation oracle computes $V(s)$ exactly for every violated subcoalition s , we set $M_s = V(s)$, which is the tightest valid choice (the constraint requires only $M_s \geq V(s)$).

PROPOSITION 2 (Stability inequality is a valid inequality for CSS). Consider a mixed-integer feasible solution (v, x, y, z, V) in the OCS model (3). (i) If (v, x, y, z, V) encodes a CSS—i.e., for every formed coalition $c(g) = \{i : z_{ig} = 1\}$ and every $s \subseteq c(g)$, $\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s)$ —then all inequalities (4) (for all g and all $s \subseteq c(g)$) are satisfied. (ii) Conversely, suppose that for some group g there exists a subset $s \subseteq c(g)$ such that $\sum_{i \in s} v_i < V(s)$. Then, for any choice of M_s with $M_s \geq V(s)$, the inequality (4) for this pair (g, s) is violated. In particular, the family (4) separates internally unstable coalitions from CSS-feasible solutions.

Proof (i) Let (v, x, y, z, V) correspond to a CSS. Fix any group $g \in G$ and subset $s \subseteq c(g)$. By definition of $c(g)$, we have $z_{ig} = 1$ for all $i \in s$, hence $|s| - \sum_{i \in s} z_{ig} = 0$, and (4) reduces to $\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s)$, which holds by internal stability of $c(g)$.

(ii) Suppose there exists a group g and a subset $s \subseteq c(g)$ with $\sum_{i \in s} v_i < V(s)$. Then, as above, we have $|s| - \sum_{i \in s} z_{ig} = 0$, so the right-hand side of (4) is exactly $V(s)$. The inequality becomes $\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s)$, which is violated by assumption. \square

Let \mathcal{F} denote the (mixed-integer) feasible set of the OCS model (3) with all designated integrality constraints enforced, and define $\mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}} := \{(v, x, y, z, V) \in \mathcal{F} : (4) \text{ holds for all } g \in G \text{ and all } s \subseteq c(g)\}$. Let \mathcal{S} denote the set of payoff vectors that admit some coalition structure with stability, i.e., $\mathcal{S} := \{v \in \mathbb{R}^N : \exists (x, y, z, V) \text{ such that } (v, x, y, z, V) \text{ encodes a CSS}\}$.

THEOREM 1 (Mixed-integer extended formulation for CSS payoffs). The mixed-integer system $(v, x, y, z, V) \in \mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}$ is an exact extended formulation for CSS payoffs in the following sense: $\text{proj}_v(\mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}) = \mathcal{S}$. In particular, maximizing $\sum_{i \in N} v_i$ over $\mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}$ yields an optimal coalition structure with stability (OCSS).

Proof (\subseteq) Let $(v, x, y, z, V) \in \mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}$ be mixed-integer feasible. The assignment variables z define a partition $CS(N) = \{c(g) : \sum_i z_{ig} > 0\}$. Constraints (3d)–(3h) ensure feasibility of the coalition-level integer programs for each group, and (3c) enforces efficiency: $\sum_{i \in c(g)} v_i = V(c(g))$ whenever $c(g)$ is nonempty. By Proposition 2(i), the family (4) implies $\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s)$ for all subsets $s \subseteq c(g)$, so each formed coalition is internally stable. Thus (v, x, y, z, V) encodes a CSS and $v \in \mathcal{S}$.

(\supseteq) Conversely, let $v \in \mathcal{S}$. By definition, there exists a coalition structure $CS(N)$ and coalition decisions x, y, V such that every coalition is efficient and internally stable. We can encode this structure by choosing integer variables z consistent with the partition ($z_{ig} = 1$ if player i belongs to coalition $c(g)$, 0 otherwise). The resulting (v, x, y, z, V) satisfies all OCS constraints and, by internal stability, all inequalities (4) for every group g and every subset $s \subseteq c(g)$. Hence $(v, x, y, z, V) \in \mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}$ and $v \in \text{proj}_v(\mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}})$. \square

Note that \mathcal{S} need not be a single polyhedron in v -space: it is, in general, a union of Core polytopes corresponding to different partitions of N . The mixed-integer system $\mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}$ therefore serves as an extended formulation for CSS payoffs rather than a direct polyhedral description in payoff space.

PROPOSITION 3 (Existence of CSS). Assume that $V(c)$ is finite for every coalition $c \subseteq N$. Then there exists at least one coalition structure with stability (CSS). In particular, the all-splinter partition $CS(N) = \{\{i\} : i \in N\}$ together with the singleton payoffs $v_i = V(\{i\})$ is a CSS.

Proof For each singleton coalition $\{i\}$, efficiency requires $v_i = V(\{i\})$, and internal stability requires $v_i \geq V(\{i\})$ for the only nonempty subcoalition $s = \{i\}$. These are compatible, so the Core of $(\{i\}, V)$ is nonempty. Collecting these singleton coalitions yields a CSS. \square

By Proposition 3, the feasible region $\mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}$ is nonempty, so solving the OCS formulation augmented with the stability inequalities (4) amounts to optimizing over CSS-feasible solutions, which leads to the OCSS.

2.5. Per-coalition solution concepts and payoff refinement

The mixed-integer system $(v, x, y, z, V) \in \mathcal{F}^{\text{stab}}$ returns a coalition structure $CS(N) = \{c(g) : \sum_{i \in N} z_{ig} > 0\}$. For each coalition $c \in CS(N)$, consider the *restricted game* (c, V_c) with characteristic function $V_c(s) := V(s)$ for all $s \subseteq c$. By construction of CSS and the stability inequalities, the Core of (c, V_c) is nonempty. We record the following classical facts for completeness.

REMARK 2 (PER-COALITION CLASSICAL SOLUTION CONCEPTS). For each coalition $c \in CS(N)$, the restricted game (c, V_c) admits the usual cooperative solution concepts: (i) the Shapley value is well-defined for (c, V_c) ; (ii) the nucleolus of (c, V_c) exists and lies in its Core; and (iii) if (c, V_c) is convex (supermodular), then the Shapley value of (c, V_c) also belongs to its Core.

The OCSS algorithm outputs one Core allocation $v^{(c)}$ per coalition, but this choice is not unique. Any other Core allocation $w^{(c)}$ of (c, V_c) can replace $v^{(c)}$ without changing the coalition structure or total welfare: redefining $v_i := w_i^{(c)}$ for $i \in c$ preserves efficiency $\sum_{i \in c} v_i = V(c)$ and all internal Core inequalities $\sum_{i \in s} v_i \geq V(s)$ for $s \subseteq c$, so the CSS constraints remain satisfied. When the Core of (c, V_c) is high-dimensional, it may be desirable to pick a “central” Core allocation rather than an arbitrary boundary point. One simple option is the max–min slack (Chebyshev-center) formulation: for each $c \in CS(N)$, choose $(\psi^{(c)}, t^{(c)})$ solving

$$\max_{\psi, t} t \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i \in c} \psi_i = V(c), \quad \sum_{i \in s} \psi_i \geq V(s) + t \quad \forall \emptyset \neq s \subseteq c, \quad t \geq 0.$$

Any optimal $\psi^{(c)}$ is a Core allocation; if $t^{(c)} > 0$, it lies in the relative interior of the Core of (c, V_c) . Applying this refinement independently to each coalition yields a CSS payoff vector whose per-coalition blocks are (in this sense) as “interior” as possible, while preserving the OCSS partition and total value.

3. Computational Methods for OCSS

Computing an optimal coalition structure with stability (OCSS) requires solving the OCS formulation (3) augmented with exponentially many stability inequalities (4). We develop three computational strategies: (i) enumeration-based cutting planes, (ii) lazy constraint callbacks, and (iii) initial heuristics for warm-starting.

3.1. Separation Strategies

Given an incumbent solution (\bar{v}, \bar{z}) , the separation oracle must identify violated stability cuts. For coalition $c(g) = \{i : \bar{z}_{ig} = 1\}$, we seek subsets $s \subseteq c(g)$ with $\sum_{i \in s} \bar{v}_i < V(s)$.

Enumeration. For small coalitions $|c(g)| \leq \tau$, we enumerate all $2^{|c(g)|} - 2$ proper nonempty subsets and check each for violation. While exponential in coalition size, this is exact and fast for $\tau \leq 10$.

Optimization-based Separation For a given group index g with coalition $c(g) = \{i \in N : \bar{z}_{ig} = 1\}$, the separation problem seeks the most violated subcoalition:

$$\max_{s \subseteq c(g)} \left\{ V(s) - \sum_{i \in s} \bar{v}_i \right\}. \tag{5}$$

If the optimal value is positive, the maximizing s^* violates stability and yields a cut; if it is nonpositive, $c(g)$ is internally stable. Problem (5) is naturally *bilevel*. The *outer* problem chooses a subset $s \subseteq c(g)$, which we encode via binary variables $\sigma_i \in \{0, 1\}$, $\sigma_i = 1 \iff i \in s$. Given s , the *inner* problem computes the coalition value $V(s)$ by solving the coalition-level integer program (2) where we reuse the item sets and availability sets. The outer-level objective can then be written as $\max_{\sigma} \left\{ V(\{i : \sigma_i = 1\}) - \sum_{i \in c(g)} \bar{v}_i \sigma_i \right\}$. Unlike classical bilevel models, no dualization is needed

here. The inner problem is a *maximization* and the outer variables σ only appear in the *right-hand sides and variable bounds* of the inner feasible region, not in its objective. This lets us embed the inner problem directly in a single-level MIP with σ -dependent bounds.

Let $c(g)$ be fixed, and define coalition-dependent sets $R_{\text{ind}}^{c(g)} := \{j \in R : |I_j \cap c(g)| = 1\}$, $R_{\text{com}}^{c(g)} := \{j \in R : |I_j \cap c(g)| \geq 2\}$. The separation problem is equivalent to the following single-level MIP, whose decision variables are the subset indicators $\sigma_i \in \{0, 1\}$ for $i \in c(g)$, the player-level item usage $x_j^i \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, and the coalition-level common-item usage $y_j \in \mathbb{Z}_+$:

$$\max \quad \sum_{i \in c(g)} \sum_{j \in R_i} p_j^i x_j^i - \sum_{i \in c(g)} \bar{v}_i \sigma_i, \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{j \in R_{\text{ind}}^{c(g)}} \sum_{i \in I_j \cap c(g)} a_j x_j^i + \sum_{j \in R_{\text{com}}^{c(g)}} a_j y_j \leq \sum_{i \in c(g)} b^i \sigma_i, \quad (6b)$$

$$y_j = \sum_{i \in I_j \cap c(g)} x_j^i, \quad \forall j \in R_{\text{com}}^{c(g)}, \quad (6c)$$

$$0 \leq x_j^i \leq u_j^i \sigma_i, \quad \forall i \in c(g), \forall j \in R_i, \quad (6d)$$

$$y_j \leq \sum_{i \in I_j \cap c(g)} u_j^i \sigma_i, \quad \forall j \in R_{\text{com}}^{c(g)}, \quad (6e)$$

$$x_j^i \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \quad y_j \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \quad \forall i, j; \quad \sigma_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in c(g). \quad (6f)$$

An optimal value of (6a) identifies the most violated stability cut; if non-positive, the current solution is stable.

3.2. Lazy Constraint Implementation

Rather than iteratively re-solving the OCS master after each round of cuts, we embed separation in Gurobi's branch-and-bound using lazy constraints. Whenever an integer-feasible solution (\bar{v}, \bar{z}) is found (callback type MIPSOL), we: (i) extract the implied coalition structure $CS(N) = \{c(g) : \bar{z}_{ig} = 1\}$, (ii) run the separation oracle for each coalition $c(g)$, and (iii) add any violated stability inequalities (4) via `cbLazy()`.

In this way, every accepted incumbent is CSS-feasible, and the search directly optimizes over CSSs. For large instances and finite time limits, the implementation ensures that the solver returns the best CSS-feasible solution found so far with a valid upper bound from the branch-and-bound tree.

3.3. Initial Heuristics

To guide the MIP search, we use two greedy heuristics that quickly propose coalition structures and associated payoff vectors. These heuristics are used only as warm starts: they typically provide good objective values but *do not* guarantee CSS-feasibility. When a heuristic solution is passed to the OCSS model, Gurobi either rejects it as infeasible (once lazy cuts are activated) or accepts it temporarily and then calls the separation routine to add violated stability cuts. In all cases, the final incumbent reported by the solver is CSS-feasible.

Bottom-up. Start from the all-splinter partition $\{\{i\} : i \in N\}$ and repeatedly merge the pair of coalitions (c_1, c_2) that yields the largest positive gain $V(c_1 \cup c_2) - V(c_1) - V(c_2)$, until no improving merge remains.

Top-down. Start from the grand coalition $\{N\}$ and recursively split coalitions. For a coalition c , consider candidate bipartitions (c_1, c_2) and apply the split with the largest positive gain $V(c_1) + V(c_2) - V(c)$, until no improving split exists.

Both heuristics require at most $O(|N|^2)$ coalition-value evaluations and play a purely algorithmic role as fast, structure-aware warm starts for the OCSS MIP.

3.4. Algorithm Summary

Algorithm 1 summarizes our approach, which combines hybrid separation (enumeration and optimization-based), lazy constraints within branch-and-bound, and heuristic warm-starts.

Algorithm 1 Cutting-plane algorithm for OCSS via lazy constraints

Require: CIPG instance, threshold τ , time limit T

Ensure: OCSS solution or best found

- 1: $(\bar{v}, CS(N)) \leftarrow \text{INITIALHEURISTIC}(\text{instance})$ {Run bottom-up and top-down, select better}
 - 2: Build OCS model (3); encode $CS(N)$ in \bar{z} and set warm-start $(\bar{v}, \bar{z}) \leftarrow (\bar{v}, \bar{z})$
 - 3: Enable lazy constraints; register separation callback
 - 4: **Callback** at mixed-integer solution (\bar{v}, \bar{z}) :
 - 5: **for** each coalition $c(g)$ with $|c(g)| \geq 2$ **do**
 - 6: **if** $|c(g)| \leq \tau$ **then**
 - 7: Enumerate all nonempty proper $s \subset c(g)$; for each violated s , add stability cut (4) via `cbLazy()`
 - 8: **else**
 - 9: Solve separation MIP (6) for $c(g)$; let s^* be the maximizing subset
 - 10: **if** objective > 0 **then**
 - 11: Add the stability cut (4) for (g, s^*) via `cbLazy()`
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: **end for**
 - 15: Solve the OCS MIP with lazy constraints and time limit T
 - 16: **return** Best incumbent solution (CSS-feasible; OCSS if optimality is certified)
-

4. Experimental design and results

Our experiments have three main goals: (i) compare OCS and OCSS in terms of objectives and coalition partitions, (ii) examine how the budget ratio ρ and pooling parameter α shape coalition patterns and the number of stability cuts required, and (iii) benchmark different algorithmic configurations for computing OCSS (enumeration-based separation, lazy constraints, and lazy constraints with heuristic warm-start). Following our CIPG framework and the OCSS algorithm, we instantiate a *Cooperative Knapsack Game* (CKG) as a testbed. Each player solves an individual knapsack problem of the form (1). In all experiments we consider $|N| \in \{4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14\}$ players and $|R| = 25$ items. Every item is available to every player, so all items are common. For each available pair $(i, j) \in N \times R$ we draw profits $p_j^i \sim U\{10, 100\}$, and for each item $j \in R$ we draw a weight $a_j \sim U\{5, 10\}$. For each player i we compute the total weight of available items and set a knapsack capacity $b^i = \rho \sum_{j \in R} a_j$, with budget ratio $\rho \in \{0.3, 0.5, 0.8\}$.

At the coalition level we use α -restricted pooling with $\alpha = 0.5$: only a fraction of the pooled capacity is available to each group g , $\sum_{j \in R} a_j y_j^g \leq \alpha \sum_{i \in N} b^i z_{ig}$, so superadditivity does not hold and non-trivial coalition structures arise. For each parameter combination $(|N|, \rho)$ we generate one random instance and solve the OCS and OCSS models, recording objectives, coalition structures, runtimes, and the number of stability cuts. All experiments were run on a workstation with an

Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-13900F CPU at 3.10GHz (24 cores) and 64GB RAM. Models were implemented in Python and solved with Gurobi 11.0.3 using up to 16 threads. In Algorithm 1 we set $\tau = 5$ and a time limit of 300 seconds.

4.1. Computational Results

We test three algorithmic configurations for computing OCSS. The first, ‘enum’, solves the OCS model and iteratively adds stability cuts by enumerating all subcoalitions of each formed group; it re-solves after each round of cuts until no violated inequality remains. The second and third, ‘lazy’ and ‘lazy+ws’, solve the OCSS problem directly in a single branch-and-bound using lazy constraint callbacks (Algorithm 1), with ‘lazy+ws’ additionally seeded with a heuristic warm-start solution. For small instances ($n \leq 10$) all three configurations are tested; for larger instances ($n > 10$) we omit enumeration due to the exponential number of subcoalitions.

For brevity, we use the following abbreviations in the tables: n : number of players; ρ : budget ratio; ‘Obj’: objective value (OCS and OCSS objectives coincide in all runs); T_{OCS} , T_{enum} , T_{lazy} , $T_{\text{lazy+ws}}$: solution times (seconds) for OCS and for OCSS under the three settings; $\text{Cuts}_{\text{enum}}$, $\text{Cuts}_{\text{lazy}}$, $\text{Cuts}_{\text{lazy+ws}}$: number of stability cuts added; ‘OCSS_Partition’: coalition structure in the final OCSS solution.

Tables 2 and 3 report the results for small and larger instances, respectively. In both tables, OCS and OCSS objectives are virtually identical. This is consistent with the Core interpretation: whenever the per-coalition Core is nonempty, one can stabilize payoffs without degrading the global objective. For small budgets ($\rho = 0.3$), the optimal coalition structure tends to favor the grand coalition or a few large coalitions; as ρ increases to 0.5 and 0.8, smaller coalitions and even self-coalitions become optimal, reflecting the loss of superadditivity under α -restricted pooling.

Table 2 shows that ‘lazy’ dominates the other two settings in terms of runtime, while ‘lazy+ws’ uses the fewest stability cuts on average. The lazy-constraint approach is effective because it switches to the optimization-based separation strategy whenever the coalition size exceeds the threshold τ (here, $\tau = 5$). Enumeration is straightforward for small instances but becomes impractical for $n > 10$ due to the exponentially many subcoalitions. Although ‘lazy+ws’ typically adds fewer stability cuts than ‘lazy’, its reported solve time includes the overhead of computing the heuristic warm-start solution, which accounts for the longer total times observed in some instances.

Table 3 exhibits a similar pattern. The ‘lazy’ setting is typically fastest, but ‘lazy+ws’ still requires fewer cuts on average. Both lazy configurations yield a modest number of stability cuts, representing a substantial reduction compared to naive enumeration. For example, in the case $n = 12$, $\rho = 0.3$, there exists a coalition of size 10; a pure enumeration scheme would inspect $2^{10} - 2$ subcoalitions, whereas ‘lazy’ and ‘lazy+ws’ add only 80 and 96 cuts, respectively.

Key findings. (1) The optimization-based separation oracle enables scaling beyond the range where enumeration is viable. (2) The lazy-constraint implementation provides the best runtimes across our tests. (3) Simple constructive heuristics yield strong warm-start coalition structures, which reduces the number of stability cuts needed, even though CSS-feasibility is ultimately enforced by the lazy cuts. (4) Under partially restricted bounds, nontrivial coalition structures arise, highlighting the need for explicit coalition-structure optimization.

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Table 2 CKG results for small instances

n	ρ	Obj	T_{OCS}	T_{enum}	T_{lazy}	$T_{\text{lazy+ws}}$	Cuts _(enum)	Cuts _(lazy)	Cuts _(lazy+ws)	OCSS.Partition
4	0.3	2628	0.13	0.25	0.17	0.24	7	7	0	[(0,1,2,3)]
	0.5	3862	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.14	0	7	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3)]
	0.8	5062	0.11	0.09	0.10	0.13	0	7	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3)]
6	0.3	3870	0.30	1.17	0.35	0.62	47	1	0	[(0,1,2,3,4,5)]
	0.5	5698	0.62	0.60	0.61	0.89	0	13	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5)]
	0.8	7472	0.24	0.20	0.27	0.39	0	9	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5)]
8	0.3	5197	0.81	4.10	0.83	1.76	158	1	0	[(0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7)]
	0.5	7611	5.56	5.51	6.44	6.11	0	77	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7)]
	0.8	9968	0.85	0.85	1.88	2.02	0	54	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7)]
10	0.3	6659	2.13	12.45	1.99	4.83	815	1	1	[(0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9)]
	0.5	9709	11.45	11.28	10.85	16.26	0	60	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7),(8),(9)]
	0.8	12628	2.59	2.49	6.62	9.99	0	116	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7),(8),(9)]
Avg			2.07	3.26	2.52	3.61	85.6	29.4	0.1	

Table 3 CKG results for large instances

n	ρ	Obj	T_{OCS}	T_{lazy}	$T_{\text{lazy+ws}}$	Cuts _(lazy)	Cuts _(lazy+ws)	OCSS.Partition
12	0.3	8108	10.47	35.14	50.17	80	96	[(8),(9),(0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,10,11)]
	0.5	11769	36.06	25.00	57.82	90	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7),(8),(9),(10),(11)]
	0.8	15321	11.62	15.75	41.19	88	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7),(8),(9),(10),(11)]
14	0.3	9504	43.85	121.75	132.21	121	72	[(3),(4),(8),(12),(0,1,2,5,6,7,9,10,11,13)]
	0.5	13801	48.28	41.91	211.27	68	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7),(8),(9),(10),(11),(12),(13)]
	0.8	17957	29.30	50.01	189.20	218	0	[(0),(1),(2),(3),(4),(5),(6),(7),(8),(9),(10),(11),(12),(13)]
Avg			29.93	48.26	113.64	110.8	28.0	

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